

Challenges and Strategies in Educating Learner's With Disability During Covid-19 Pandemic

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ABSTRACT

The study titled *Challenges and Strategies in Educating Learners with Disabilities During the Covid-19 Pandemic* aimed to explore the difficulties encountered by teachers and the strategies they employed to ensure effective learning among students with disabilities. Specifically, the objectives were to identify the challenges teachers faced, determine the strategies they used, and highlight the most effective approaches across different schools. Data gathered revealed several challenges, including disobedience of students to parental guidance, frequent behavior tantrums, selectivity in accepting instruction, difficulty in developing modules and

activities, questionable reliability of student responses to modules, ineffectiveness of online platforms, short attention spans, and limitations in the learning environment. To address these, teachers implemented various strategies such as monitoring students through group chat messages, video calls, and phone calls; conducting weekly orientations with parents to provide guidance on lesson execution and activities; modifying modules; conducting house-to-house visitations; using big books and talking books; offering and delivering modules every 15 days; rewarding students through virtual recognition; holding one-hour online classes; and incorporating songs to capture attention. Among these, the most effective strategies varied by school: School A found group chat monitoring most effective, School B emphasized the modular approach, School C preferred delivering modules every 15 days, and School D identified one-hour online classes as the most impactful. These findings highlight the adaptability of teachers in overcoming pandemic-related barriers and underscore the importance of context-specific strategies in supporting learners with disabilities.

Keywords: *Covid-19 Pandemic, Learners With Disabilities, Teaching Challenges, Teaching Strategies, Modular Learning, Online Learning, Parental Involvement, Attention Span, Behavior Management, Inclusive Education, Teacher Adaptability, Group Chat Monitoring, Module Delivery, Virtual Recognition, Educational Environment*

INTRODUCTION

CoVid-19 has wreaked havoc on education systems around the world, causing unprecedented problems and changes. People are anxious about this issue since the number of deaths and sick patients increases every day. As a result, academic institutions were shut in order to reduce student-employee contact, and children were physically and socially isolated.

In light of the aforementioned dilemma in education, distance learning has been implemented. And to ensure educational continuity, the use of technology and internet-based education was established. However, it is undeniable that not all learners have the same situation and abilities to cope with the problem. School closures have a significant impact on all learners, especially on learners with disability, who are more likely to confront additional challenges. They may have difficulty in using technology, limited access to educational resources and tailored learning interventions, and a loss of social relationships. Little information was given to their situation during this pandemic. Online studying is difficult for ordinary learners; and more so for learners who need more attention, priority, and need.

Umesh Sharma, an Educational Psychologist and Inclusive Education professor said that about 1.6 billion learners throughout the world have been unable to attend school due to lockdowns and schools continuing to make modifications in online education. In the Philippines, around three million children are not enrolled in primary school (Cite reference). Uaminal, (2020) asserts that this number is nearly equivalent to the total population of Quezon City (2.94 million). What about learners with disability, are they still studying?

The 1987 Philippine Constitution, the Child and Youth Welfare Code (PD 603), the Special Protection of Children Against Child Abuse, Exploitation, and Discrimination Act (RA 7610), the Early Years Act (RA 10410), the Enhanced Basic Education Act (RA 10533), the Magna Carta for Disabled Persons amended by RA 9442 (RA 7277), and the Policies and Guidelines in Education (RA 10533) all require the adoption of an Inclusive Education (IE) approach. And, the core of Inclusive Education is the fundamental human right of the younger generation to education. Inclusion in education is viewed as “a dynamic approach of responding positively to pupil diversity and of seeing individual differences not as problems, but as opportunities for enriching learning” (UNESCO, 2005). Inclusion is defined as a process of addressing and responding to the diverse needs of all learners by increasing participation in learning, cultures, and communities and decreasing exclusion within and from education. It entails changes and modifications in content, approaches, structures, and strategies, with a common vision that encompasses all children of the appropriate age range and the conviction that it is the regular system's responsibility to educate all children (UNESCO 2005).

Even as the educational system shifts to the online mode of learning, the government, institutions, schools, and teachers must adapt to it. Regardless of the pandemic, parents and other members of society must pay attention, support, and make an attempt to provide a good and proper education for learners with disability.

That is why the researchers made this study. They believe that inclusive education means that all learners are valued and get a high-quality, equitable education. Furthermore, SDG 4 on inclusive and equitable quality education and promotion of life-long learning opportunities for everyone focuses on eradicating gender inequities in education and ensuring equal access to a quality education for all.

It is crucial to investigate the various problems and techniques employed by parents and teachers in educating learners with disability, especially in these times of pandemic. There is a little information about learners with disability, as well as how their parents and teachers cope with the problems in order to educate them. Thus, this study would delve into their situation during the CoVid-19 pandemic.

The purpose of this study was to shed light on how learners with disabilities are faring in these pandemic times. Also, it aimed to identify the issues and strategies that their teachers employ to educate them.

Statement of the Problem

The purpose of this research is to identify the challenges and strategies in educating learners with disability during the Covid-19 Pandemic.

Furthermore, the purpose of this research is to provide a response to the following questions:

1. What are the various challenges that teachers are facing in educating learners with disability this pandemic?
2. What are the various strategies that teachers employ in educating learners with disability this pandemic?
3. What is the most effective strategies among those employed by teachers in educating learners with disability this pandemic?

Scope and Delimitation

The purpose of this study was to identify the challenges and strategies that teachers face in teaching learners with disability during the Covid-19 pandemic.

The researchers selected learners with disability because they are among those children who have been most impacted by the abrupt change in educational pedagogy brought about by Covid-19.

This study's respondents will be special education teachers from several schools in Daet, Camarines Norte and the parents of learners with disability.

This study was conducted from August to December 2021 in Daet, a first-class municipality and the capital of the province of Camarines Norte.

Significance of the Study

The findings of the study will significantly benefit the following:

Camarines Norte State College. This study will help the school in its pursuit to become a university. CNSC may be able to use this study as a reference to understand the importance of inclusive education. In addition, CNSC may construct its own inclusive education department and building in the future.

Parents. They will learn better ways to handle and teach their children. Parents may also assume that they are not alone in their challenges with educating their children, especially during the Covid-19 pandemic. This research can serve as a guide on how they can treat their children and what methods are most effective in educating them.

Teachers. This research will help special education teachers discover how to properly educate learners with disability this pandemic, especially those new in the teaching profession. Also, they will be able to develop their abilities. They can formulate ways to come up with support mechanisms to parents.

Students. This study will motivate high school and college students to continue their studies. It will teach them to appreciate the fact that they are privileged learners with more ability and comprehension. Many children nowadays find studying difficult, leading them to give up or complain. Nevertheless, this study will demonstrate how much more difficult it is for learners with disabilities to study and comprehend lessons, not just for them but also for their parents and teachers.

Department of Education. They may also provide workshops on how to educate learners with disability to promote and support teachers and parents.

Future Researcher's. This work will help future researchers gain knowledge. This could potentially be their linked study.

Definition of Terms

Challenges. It refers to a difficult experience for parents and teachers to educate learners with disability during online education. This refers to the situation being faced with something that needs great mental or physical effort in order to be done successfully and therefore tests a person's ability. (Cambridge Dictionary)

Strategy. It refers to the methods or techniques used by teachers to educate learners with disability during online education. It refers to the detailed plan for achieving success in situations such as war, politics, business, industry, sports, or the skill of planning for such situation. It is also a way of doing something or dealing with something. (Cambridge dictionary)

Learners with Disability. It refers to students who are not typical or have illnesses that make it difficult for them to learn; it can be a slow learner or gifted students. It refers to the learners with learning, physical and

developmental disabilities; behavioral, emotional, and communication disorders and learning deficiencies. (Oxford Academic Dictionary)

Special Education. It refers to a school that serves students with disabilities. This refers to the education of children who differ socially, mentally, or physically from the average to such an extent that they require modifications of usual school practices. Special education serves children with emotional, behavioral, or cognitive impairments or with intellectual, hearing, vision, speech, or learning disabilities; gifted children with advanced academic abilities; and children with orthopedic or neurological impairments.

Covid 19. It refers to a virus that has spread throughout the world, causing people to avoid going out and all establishments and institutions to close. It refers to the infectious disease caused by the SARS-CoV-2 virus. Most people infected with the virus will experience mild to moderate respiratory illness and recover without requiring special treatment. However, some will become seriously ill and require medical attention. Older people and those with underlying medical conditions like cardiovascular disease, diabetes, chronic respiratory disease, or cancer are more likely to develop serious illness. Anyone can get sick with COVID-19 and become seriously ill or die at any age. (World Health Organization)

Pandemic. It refers to a disease that has spread throughout the world, killing millions of people; it is dangerous and frightening. This refers to a disease outbreak that spreads across countries or continents. It affects more people and takes more lives than an epidemic. The World Health Organization (WHO) declared COVID-19 to be a pandemic when it became clear that the illness was severe and that it was spreading quickly over a wide area. (World Health Organization)

Online Education. It refers to a type of learning that takes place online through the use of online platforms. Online education is a flexible instructional delivery system that encompasses any kind of learning that takes place via the Internet (Encyclopedia)

LITERATURE REVIEW

Strategies In Educating Learners with Disability

Bull & Jerge, (2021) in their study entitled *Severe Cognitive Disabilities in Online Learning: Creating Effective Engagement in a Remote Setting* examined the various strategies used during remote learning for high school students with Severe Cognitive Disabilities (SCDs) in order to identify which ones are most beneficial in terms of engagement. Individual student observations were done throughout online learning class sessions using approaches from their past research. The study revealed that giving students the opportunity to demonstrate their knowledge, providing choices, working with others, and having a self-selected objective to strive toward were some of the most critical variables for improved engagement.

Crouse, Rice, Mellard (2020) in their study entitled “*Learning to Serve Students with Disabilities Online: Teachers’ Perspective*”, six completely online teachers from various grade levels and topic areas were asked to explain and reflect on the strategies they utilized to address the educational needs of students with disabilities, as

well as how they learned them. Despite receiving little to no education in working with students with disabilities online before taking a position as an online instructor, the teachers mentioned several technology and relational tools they employed to support their students that went beyond legal accommodation. The teachers, on the other hand, were unable to articulate particular teaching approaches for learners with impairments, nor could they mention specific regulations or legalities pertaining to these learners. However, they hoped that they had more professional development opportunities so that they could share their experience with others. Teachers may also benefit from tailored help that draws on relevant traditional experience and adapts it for use in an online setting. As a result, teacher preparation programs may consider how collaborating with and maintaining research relationships with online schools, as well as experiences with students with disabilities, can help attract more qualified teachers to online learning and provide better support for these teachers to remain in their jobs.

Challenges in Educating Learners with Disability

Toquero, (2021) in his study entitled ‘Sana All’ Inclusive Education amid COVID-19: Challenges, Strategies, and Prospects of Special Education Teachers argued that teachers must optimize the education of learners with unique educational requirements and disabilities despite this pandemic. There are educational, social, and psychological barriers that pose difficulties in teachers' pedagogical instruction through emergency remote teaching as a result of the outbreak, but there are also ways to help people with Special Educational Needs and Disabilities (SEND) learn. People with SEND can benefit from measures such as internet communication, homeschooling, parental engagement, psychological safety, and empathy language to help them continue their educational pursuits in the face of an emergency. Furthermore, schools' policies and standards must be inclusive so that people with SEND can benefit from the government's educational programs. The government's initiatives should consider both the children's educational needs and SEND. People with SEND should not be overlooked because they are future generations who can make a positive difference in society. People with developmental disabilities have the power to shape post-pandemic society if they are given the learning spaces and stakeholder support, they need right now to thrive in the midst of the pandemic.

In the study of Latzer, Itay, Karnieli-Miller, & Orit, (2021) entitled “Core Experiences of Parents of Children with Autism during the COVID-19 Pandemic Lockdown” identified the main experiences of parents of autistic children throughout this big life disruption. Thirty-one parents of 25 autistic children took part in semi-structured telephone interviews, which were transcribed verbatim and analyzed qualitatively using immersion/crystallization. During the lockdown, an iterative consensus-building approach was used to determine parents' experiences, concerns, obstacles, coping techniques, and perceived requirements. The main themes that emerged were the various parental concerns, the major problems encountered during this one-of-a-kind period, the functional, social, and behavioral ramifications of the lockdown on these children, and the parents' ingenuity and attitude. Their findings contribute to our understanding of the fundamental factors that influence how autistic children and their parents deal with adversity in their lives. In such cases, programs should concentrate on assisting and guiding parents on how to better adapt to the situation, thereby improving their coping skills and resilience.

Meanwhile the study of Allam, Fely, & Matronillo (2021) entitled “Issues and Challenges in Special Education: A Qualitative Analysis from Teacher's Perspective” identified the concerns and challenges faced by special education (SPED) instructors in the City Division of Ilagan Isabela, Philippines, when teaching learners

with learning disabilities. Purposive sampling was used to select the 15 SPED teachers who would participate in this study. The authors discovered that classrooms for learners with learning difficulties in the entire Division of Ilagan have poor learning environments, including a lack of funding, curriculum guide, Instructional Materials (IMs), and even school facilities. It could be inferred that placing special needs learners in an inclusive classroom with other learners is insufficient without suitable support.

Based on the article Challenges of online learning for students with special needs by Illinois Public Media (April 27, 2020). Their families have struggled with so-called "e-learning," which can be even more difficult for learners with disability. As schools rely on parents and caregivers to conduct remote education for students, many families in Illinois have had to figure out their new responsibilities as both parent and teacher. The transition from caregiver to educator, on the other hand, can be extremely difficult for parents of learners with disabilities. Learners with disabilities and their families frequently rely on the school system's individualized support services. This could range from speech pathologists to one-on-one nursing. Many of those support services, however, have vanished as a result of the closure of school facilities.

Practices In Addressing Challenges

In the study of Adams, Harris, Jones (2016) entitled "Teacher-Parent Collaboration for an Inclusive Classroom: Success for Every Child", collaboration between teachers and parents in special educational practices should be encouraged, and everyone involved in a child's life should work together to provide the greatest education possible. Indeed, the significant stakeholders in a child's life may hold disparate opinions and beliefs, which can lead to a breakdown in communication and relationships. In such circumstances, fluid collaborations among various stakeholders can be difficult, and tensions can arise, affecting a child's educational experience. The authors used a variety of evidence sources, including interviews with instructors and parents, as well as questionnaires, to investigate this topic. The perspectives of teachers and parents provide fascinating insights into how actual collaboration occurred in the classrooms.

Sari, Widyantoro & Octavia (2021) posit that the online program heavily relies on parents to give full-time learning support for their children. Parents are now in charge of a variety of measures that can encourage and facilitate their children's transition to online learning. Even highly engaged parents, on the other hand, were under enormous pressure to adapt successfully and adequately to such a change. Online educators should learn more about the needs of their students and use appropriate strategies to help them. As a result, online educators must foster an open, engaging, and learner-centered environment in which students can freely share their ideas, opinions, and concerns. Furthermore, socioeconomic status could be included because it has the potential to influence parents' participation in online learning. Future research should concentrate on better understanding parental engagement in a variety of settings, including those with varying educational levels and learner characteristics.

Stenhoff, Pennington & Tapp, (2020) said that schools play an important role for learners with autism spectrum disorder (ASD) and other disability. However, due to pandemic, natural disasters, and school shootings, school-based instruction may be disrupted, forcing schools to suspend regular services and begin teaching students from home. When rural schools close, they face unique challenges, such as proximity to students and technological limitations. This paper outlines how instructors can create educational materials, communication supports, and

behavioral supports. It also explained how careers can provide support and how caregivers can be educated on the skills required to provide successful support. When rural schools close, they face unique challenges, such as proximity to students and technological limitations. Despite the fact that 63 percent of rural homes have broadband internet, a sizable proportion of them do not have access to online distance learning. This article demonstrated the importance of teachers being adaptable when it comes to their students' educational needs. It addressed issues that teachers should consider when planning and delivering instruction.

Strategies in Educating Learners with Disability

Yazcayir, & Gurgur, (2021) in their study entitled *Students with Special Needs in Digital Classrooms during the COVID-19 Pandemic in Turkey* sought to see how special education for students in inclusive schools has continued at home during the pandemic. According to participants, some teachers held online sessions and exchanged worksheets with all students via the WhatsApp group. However, a number of concerns have been raised, including the fact that learners with disabilities were unable to regularly follow the courses on television, that many of them did not attend online lessons, and that their lecturers did not provide feedback on their efforts. Furthermore, no special education support services were provided to students, and there was no communication or cooperation among instructors, families, or students. Furthermore, the findings revealed that students were hesitant and unable to adapt to distance learning.

Cheng & Lai, (2020) in their study *Facilitating Learning for Students with Special Needs: A Review of Technology Supported Special Education Studies* stated that learners with disability often have more difficulty learning due to physical or mental problems. Researchers have implemented technology-supported methods to improve impaired students' adaptation to the learning environment and their learning achievement in an effort to improve their learning. In recent years, the use of technology-assisted special education has steadily increased. However, research and analysis of the use and development patterns of integrating technologies into special education are still lacking. Technology is being employed in every learning domain, but it is mostly aimed at elementary school learners and resource classrooms. Most importantly, the deployment of technology-assisted special education does not tend to cause instructional challenges as a result of learners with disability with various types and levels of disabilities.

The study of Gatot Jariono, et.al, (Look for complete authors and year) entitled “*Strategies to Teach Children with Special Needs Amid COVID-19 pandemic* examined and characterized the instructional strategies used by special needs children. The findings of this study show that teachers teaching learners with disability during the COVID-19 pandemic in either category or 67.5 percent strongly agree to use online-based learning by involving parental participation consist of parents participating in the online learning process accompanies learners with disability, teachers and parents of one unit who synergize in accompanying, guiding, motivators, etc. Further research is needed in this study by including numerous aspects, including the social environment, social relations, physical activity exercises based on the characteristics of children, stakeholders, and teaching and learning processes in the COVID-19 outbreak.

The study of Tzivinikou & Papoutsaki (2015) entitled *Studying Teaching Methods, Strategies and Best Practices for Young Children with Special Educational needs* shows that special education instruction differ from those of a regular classroom. Individual learning, achievement, and growth are prioritized by educational

programmers for special needs kids. As a result, instruction in inclusive schools' special education classrooms and resource rooms must be detailed, directed, and personalized. The study found that the participants' self-reported data indicated that they were concerned about their students' learning outcomes and that they used successful teaching methods, approaches, and strategies, but that this was not supported by observational data.

Wheatley (2021) in his study Perceptions of Special Education Services Delivered through Online Learning Environments during COVID-19 revealed that many people have questioned how special education services should be offered to learners with disabilities as a result of the change to online learning. The goal of this study was to see how people felt about special education services provided in a remote learning setting during a public health emergency. A total of 108 teachers, related service providers, and parents of learners with disabilities were questioned across the United States. The most common method of offering special education services was synchronous online learning, according to the findings. Participants, on the other hand, overwhelmingly believed that online training was inefficient in providing quality services to students with impairments. Implications for improving online services for learners with disabilities could include determining the exact reasons for participants' unfavorable attitudes, which could lead to more meaningful measures in improving online learning in the future. Furthermore, investigating school actions that have resulted in good perceptions of online learning among parents and educators could be used to improve perceptions of online education for children with disabilities. Future research directions are also highlighted.

The study of Sholikhati, Prayogo & Santoso (2021) entitled The Effect of Distance Learning on Learning Outcomes of Children with Special Needs in Inclusive Schools in the New Normal revealed that distant learning affected learners with disabilities in inclusive schools in the new normal period. According to the study's findings, remote learning, which is used in Yogyakarta's inclusive primary schools, is learning that is done online using a variety of learning resources, both on and off the internet network. Course materials are distributed online, communication is conducted online, and all exams are administered online. According to the results of implementing distance learning in inclusive primary schools, learning the Indonesian language remotely has a positive influence on learners with disabilities' acquisition of reading, hearing, writing, and speaking competencies during the Covid-19 cycle.

Challenges in Educating Learners with Disability

Nordin, Iqbal and Bajwa (2021) in his study entitled Challenges of Parents in The Implementation of Teaching Process and Facilitation at Home During Movement Control Order for Students with Special Needs with Hearing Impairment in Malaysia claimed that dealing with the COVID19 pandemic is a difficult moment in their lives. To manage the pandemic's chain of transmission, the government had to issue a Movement Control Order (PKP). The learning of students has been hampered as a result of school closures across the country. Students with special needs (MBK) are in a similar situation across the country. To ensure that students continue to learn, special education teachers must run the PDPc process from home to MBK. If ordinary students face difficulties accepting and implementing lessons at home, the MBK and the students' parents face even greater difficulties. Constraints include a lack of adequate hardware, expertise in dealing with this situation, remote PDPc operation skills, and commitment. In contrast, the parents are the most important factor in the process's success. In order to carry out PDPc and ensure that hearing MBK is always learned, parents must be prepared in a variety of ways. As a result,

this research should be conducted to assist parents and families of hearing MBK students in preparing to assist in this ongoing learning process.

Practices in Addressing Challenges

Hanover Research (2020) in his study entitled Best Practices for Addressing Challenges in Special Education in Distance Learning stated that the following are the best practices gathered by the study. Teachers should investigate realistic ways to implement the instructional accommodations and curriculum changes stated in student IEPs while adhering to the plan's criteria. As a starting point, they should incorporate broader best practices in online instruction for students with disabilities, and administrators should direct instructors on how to do so. For example, questions and curricula for distance learning may have universal design characteristics. Effective special educators and school administrators work hard to foster a strong sense of community among disabled students and their families. This includes recognizing the additional challenges that learners with disabilities and their families face as a result of distance learning, as well as providing ongoing positive support and social opportunities to maintain human connections. Simultaneously, instructors and other staff who engage with children with disabilities should restore expectations and routines within the new learning format, as well as teach, model, and re-teach new behaviors that will occur during virtual learning that students may be unfamiliar with. Special educators must continue to use evidence-based techniques and consider those online-specific behaviors that require explicit instruction, modeling, and reinforcement for students with disabilities to fulfill related IEP goals.

The study of Benigno, Guistro, Silvaggio and Sperandio (2020) entitled E-inclusion: Online Special Education in Italy during the Covid-19 found out that all learners with disability must be integrated into regular classes through collaboration between class and special education teachers, according to Italian law. Following the closure of schools in February 2020 due to the Covid-19 epidemic, teachers had to collaborate to plan online inclusive activities for all of their students. The findings show that effective e-inclusion is dependent on technology, family relationships, teacher collaboration, and online teaching strategies; in particular, teachers had to create personalized activities for students to engage in, preferably in small groups and individually, using asynchronous and synchronous interactive ways.

Ribeiro et.al (2021) in his study entitled Parental Involvement during Pandemic Times: Challenges and Opportunities stated that many countries established emergency preparations, such as lockdown and school closures, as a result of COVID-19. This new situation has had a significant impact on families, particularly on the level of involvement required to support children's learning at home. The purpose of this study was to determine how Portuguese parents perceived their home-based parental involvement in their children's learning during the COVID-19 lockdown and school closures in 2020. Data were collected from 21,333 parents of students ranging in age from elementary to secondary school, and statistical data were analyzed using IBM SPSS Statistics 26. The findings show that parents, particularly those with primary school children, must devote a significant amount of time to their children's education, making it difficult to balance work or telework with school activities. Implications for policies, schools, and families are being investigated in order to improve children's learning and achievement.

Synthesis State-of-the-Art

Strategies In Educating Learners with Disability

Our research focuses on a variety of topics, including the challenges and strategies used by teachers and parents to educate students with special needs. There are a variety of strategies that are beneficial to the learning of students with learning, physical, and developmental disabilities; behavioral, emotional, and communication disorders; and learning deficiencies, as opposed to the study of Strategies in Educating Learners with Disability, which only focused on learners with Severe Cognitive Disabilities and searched only for the best teacher strategy to create terms of engagement of students.

Challenges in Educating Learners with Disability

The above-mentioned study focused solely on the challenges faced by parents of autistic children, including parents' experiences in educating their children, obstacles to overcome, and discovered coping strategies. While our research focused on the difficulties faced by teachers and parents. How teachers came up with different types of strategies that can be adopted or used by parents to make it easier for them to cope with the changing teaching-learning process of their child where they as a teacher during distance learning.

Practices In Addressing Challenges

Our research focuses on the role of teachers as educators as well as learners with special needs in the midst of a pandemic, as well as their challenges and strategies. Despite the distance between teaching and learning, teachers can still play an important role in creating a conducive learning environment for students and assisting parents of students with special needs in properly handling and educating their children at home. While the study in Practices in Addressing Challenges only identifies the difficulties and efforts of parents in educating their children with special needs in the midst of a pandemic.

Strategies In Educating Learners with Disability

According to the studies written above, when the COVID-19 pandemic occurs, there are schools that use online based learning during distance learning in educating learners with special needs. Online sessions, such as synchronous sessions, can be held using a technology-enabled method. While our research will determine which teachers' strategies are more effective and beneficial to students with special needs. Strategies that do not solely focus on the use of technology, as learners with special needs are not always well-versed in its application. Our research will determine a strategy that will be more comfortable, understandable, and effective for the students.

Challenges in Educating Learners with Disability

Our research does not only focus on parents who serve as home teachers for their children during the distance learning mode. Our research continues to focus on the challenges that teachers face because they are still involved in the teaching and learning process of students. They are still confronted with obstacles, concerns, and

demands. While the studies mentioned above only focus on the difficulties that parents face when educating their children with special needs,

Practices In Addressing Challenges

The above-mentioned study focuses on assessing the challenges of using online instruction in the classroom for students with special needs. Learner activities are conducted online or in an asynchronous session. Students and teachers meet in real time via an online application. While our research focuses on assessing the challenges that can be overcome through the collaboration of teachers and parents in developing effective teaching and learning strategies to meet the needs of all students.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The Conceptual Framework is a pattern that shows the concepts of the study. It is composed of three factors the Input, Process and Output.

The Input consists of the following objectives: to identify the various challenges that teachers face in educating learners with disability, to determine the various strategies utilized by teachers in the education of learners with disability, and to determine the most effective strategies utilized by teachers in the education of learners with disability.

This study has two types of respondents; the teachers and the parents. The researchers, interviewed the teachers and gathered data from parents through questionnaire using Google Form.

The Output is to Determine the Challenges and Strategies in educating learners with disability during the Covid-19 pandemic.

Figure 1- Conceptual Paradigm

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

John Sweller developed and published Cognitive Load Theory (CLT) in 1988. Cognitive Load Theory has been designed to provide guidelines intended to assist in the presentation of information in a manner that encourages learner activities that optimize intellectual performance," he wrote. This theory suggested how to use brain-based to school, and it stated that the human brain has limited capacity. There are two (2) primary information processing activities: knowledge acquisition and problem-solving. These two must be separated in school, and the teacher should only focus on one or teach one at a time, because this theory also assumed that memory load theory should be reduced and schema construction encouraged.

Also, according to this theory, one of the main reasons for the ineffectiveness of problem-solving as a learning device is that the cognitive processes required by the two activities do not overlap sufficiently, and that conventional problem-solving in the form of means-ends analysis requires a relatively large amount of cognitive processing capacity, which is thus unavailable for schema acquisition. To put it another way, the fact that problem-solving and domain knowledge aren't directly proportional is due to how the human brain works. Problem-solving takes up valuable 'brain bandwidth,' reducing what is 'left' for 'learning new things.

Therefore, this has an implication for how teachers design lessons, units, and assessments, as well as how curriculum developers employ brain-based learning instructional design elements. Moreover, it is more effective that teachers are the ones who must give information or ideas to students rather than require students to discover things for themselves. Cognitive Load Theory is effective to use in special education or educating (SPED) students with special needs since SPED are not more likely to acquire information's or discover things on their own, they need guidance from teachers or their parents in learning things.

Furthermore, Robert Gagne's theory of learning describes conditions of learning as a means by which individuals and groups acquire relevant skills in order to be accepted in society. Learning is a direct result of human behavior, which is influenced by the environment as well as the learners' individual thought processes. He also stated that learning a specific skill is dependent on prior learning skills in a logical and sequential manner, which contributes to the development of a learning experience. He proposed a set of critical learning conditions, which he then regarded as important in the learning of various outcomes. In terms of internal organization in long term memory and required mental processing, these outcomes differ: verbal information, intellectual skills, cognitive strategies, motor skills, and student attitudes.

Aside from these unique learning conditions, there are nine levels of instruction that serve as a foundation for all types of learning and instructional design. These points assist educators and trainers in keeping a checklist for all teaching and training activities. Each step emphasizes a type of communication, and when one step is completed, learners tend to retain and apply the skills taught in a more effective and efficient manner. Gaining Attention (Reception), Informing Learners of the Objective (Expectancy), Stimulating Recall of Prior Learning (Retrieval), Presenting the Stimulus (Selective Perception), Providing Learning Guidance (Semantic Encoding),

Eliciting Performance (Responding), Providing Feedback (Reinforcement), Assessing Performance (Retrieval), and Improving Retention and Transfer are the nine levels (Generalization).

Gagne's Conditions of Learning is very effective in special education because it is important to consider students' skills, strategies, and attitudes before creating goals because it makes the teacher realize and know the needs of students on how activities must be made and processed.

Figure 2- Theoretical Paradigm

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

Descriptive research methods are those that describe the features of the variables being studied. This methodology focuses on answering questions on the "what" of the study issue rather than the "why." Instead of focusing on the "why," the primary goal of descriptive research is to simply describe the characteristics of the demographics under examination.(Voxco)

Sampling Design

To collect the data, the researchers used a non-random sample method known as purposive sampling, also known as judgment, selective, or subjective sampling. It is a sampling technique in which researchers use their own discretion in selecting members of the population to participate in the study.

Teachers and parents of students with disabilities were selected through this sampling method. Purposive sampling, on the other hand, may be effective when only a small number of people can serve as primary data sources due to the nature of the research design and aims and objectives.

Respondents of the Study

This study's respondents were four (4) special education teachers from several schools in Daet, Camarines Norte, and four parents from each school with a total of 16 parents of learners with disability.

This research was carried out in Daet, Camarines Norte from September to December.

Research Instrument

The researchers used unstructured interviews for teachers and Likert Scale questionnaire for parents to collect data.

Following the interview and questionnaire, we will examine, tally, and summarize the responses in order to produce credible and factual results. Our interview guide only has three (3) main questions, which are the same as our problem statement; however, there is a possibility that we will raise unexpected questions during the interview, which is why we chose to prepare an unstructured interview guide. And the questions on our questionnaire, which was sent via Google Form, differed based on the responses of different teachers at different schools to the question about what strategies they used to teach students with disabilities.

Source of the Data and Data Gathering Procedure

The primary source of data that will be acquired will be established through interviews and questionnaire, wherein the researchers will be able to gather information.

The researchers will develop a set of questions for instructors to answer via interview. And a questionnaire through the use of Google Form to ask the parents on what are the most effective strategies employed by the teachers.

Data Analysis

The inductive approach was used in the examination of research data. The information gathered through interviews and questionnaire were transcribed into writings. Researchers worked independently on these texts and coded them while comparing the emergent code clusters.

Ethical Consideration

This study forbids us from dropping or mentioning the names of the teachers we interviewed, as well as the names and identities of the parents. The researchers also blurred the photo we took during the interview, as well as the names of the parents who responded to the Google Form.

In addition, the study only included detailed descriptions based on direct quotations from participants' points of view. Participants' consents and approvals were obtained in accordance with research ethics. The researchers also informed the participants that they have the option to withdraw from the study at any time.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Challenges that teacher are facing in educating Learner's with disability these times of pandemic

Listed below are the following responses which were gathered after conducting the interview with the teacher participants:

Table 1 – Summary of the Challenges in Educating Learners with Disability

SCHOOLS	THEMES OF RESPONSES	DISCUSSION
School A School C	Disobedience to parents	STSA-1 stated that most of the parents told them that their child did not follow their commands at home, parents find it difficult to handle their child during learning or answering their modules. And also, STSA-3 mentioned that it is difficult for parents to control their children.
School A School D	Behavior Tantrums	STSA-1 said that it is very challenging to teach students because they have behavior tantrums, they suddenly cry and get mad and shouts. And, STSA-4 said that students cannot refrain the students from standing and playing while she is teaching them through online.
School A School C	Selective of whom to teach them	STSA-1 and STSA-3 said that students much prefer to be taught by their teachers than their parents, that is why students disobeyed their parents, because students are more likely to obey their teachers' commands and teachings than their parents.
School A	Reliability of responses to students' modules	STSA-1 stated that she observed and noticed that the answer in the activity is not truly students' effort or work, that is why she modified the module based on the ability of her students, so that students would find it easy and can answer it.

School A School B	Difficulty in Developing Modules and Activities	STSA-1 found it difficult to modify the module and the activity given to students. And, STSA-2 mentioned that during his meeting in the Division Office of Camarines Norte, which is in charge of Exceptional Education, struggled to develop activities and modules for learners with disability during the first school year following Covid-19 pandemic.
School C	Ineffectiveness of the use of Online Platform	STSA-3 discussed some of the challenges in educating learners with disability during this pandemic, during which teaching and learning were switched to online mode. She stated that during this time, children receive less attention because it is more effective to teach them in person; it is hard to teach learners with disability especially through online.
School D	Attention Span	STSA-4 stated that the most difficult challenges is the student's short attention span. it is difficult to capture students' attention online because students mind suddenly, absent and cannot focus well.
School D	Learning Environment	STSA-4 also added that students cannot focus well because they do not feel like they are at school.

Strategies that teachers employ in educating Learner's with disability these times of pandemic?

A. School A

STSA-1 stated that despite the difficulty in carrying out the lessons, teachers devise strategies such as orienting parents or guardians about the content of the module as well as how to teach them and suggesting effective teaching strategies to teach and handle them, modifying the modules, and teachers advising parents or guardians to get only enough module that their children can answer. Aside from the DepEd module, teachers at School A in Special Education believe that requiring parents to provide a large book for students to draw, trace numbers, and write in is an additional useful technique for students to learn. Another example is a teacher-created group chat in which parents or guardians can ask questions and receive information. Teachers frequently use group chat to send crash courses. Furthermore, teachers monitor students through phone calls, student phone calls, and house visits. In addition, the teacher recommends that parents limit their children's study time to one (1) hour per day in order for them to feel less rushed and more focused on the lecture.

B. School B

STSA-2 explained that their technique is to check and monitor children's performance in their class or activity by calling their parents, texting them, and messaging them via messenger. Through this type of action, they will also learn about the needs of students. He also stated that another technique for teaching learners with disability is to put yourself in their shoes, even if you are a professional, because doing so will help you understand the students and they will appreciate learning from you.

C. School C

STSA-3 revealed that they only deliver modules every fifteen (15) days; intended modules include English, Math, Filipino, and MAPEH, and they change. Another option is to provide talking books for students who have difficulty understanding. They also created group chats for parents to keep them up to date on their students' development and needs, as well as virtual programs or virtual recognition to recognize students' efforts and success. As a result of this recognition, students will learn more effectively.

D. School D

Due to the difficulties, STSA-4 used an online platform to teach students as well as provide modules. She has ten students and only has one hour to teach each day. Another method is that she composed a song to pique her students' interest; in her version, she simply substitutes the lyrics of twinkle, twinkle little star. For example, if the students are not paying attention and always stand, ignoring her and refusing to listen, she will sing, and her students will also answer her through a song, in this way the students will be reminded that he or she has class and to catch their attention, and because she believes that people like music, whenever people hear music, we dance, sing, and continue to listen to the song, just like any other individual, children with special needs. She also visited her students every two months to stay up to date on their progress.

TABLE SUMMARY

Table 2 – Summary of the Strategies in Educating Learners with Disability

SCHOOLS	THEMES OF RESPONSES
School A School C	Checking of students through Group Chat Messages
School A School B	Checking students via video call and phone call

School A	Having weekly Orientations for parents
School A School B School C	Module Modification
School A School D	Checking students through House-to House Visitation
School A	Using Big Books
School B	Modular Mode
School C	Delivering Modules every 15 days
School C	Using virtual recognition to reward students' work and success
School C	Using Talking Books
School D	One Hour Online Class
School D	Using Songs to capture children's attention

Most effective strategies among those employed by teachers in educating learners with disability these times of pandemic?

A. School A

The graphs below depict the responses of parents of learners with disability at School A

STSA-1 at School A uses the following strategies: checking students via group chat messages, checking students via video call and phone call, having weekly orientations for parents to discuss how to execute the lessons and give some advice on possible activities for their child, module modification, checking students via house-to-house visitation, and using big books in which students draw,

trace,

and

write.

Checking the students through group chat messages

4 responses

Figure 1.1 shows the result of how effective the strategy of checking the students through group chat messages at School A. It can be gleaned that 25% of the respondents are satisfied in the strategy, while 75% of the respondents are Very Satisfied on the said strategy.

Checking the students through video call and phone calls

4 responses

Figure 1.2 shows the result of how effective the strategy of checking the students through vide call ang phone call at School A. It can be gleaned that 50% of the respondents answered neutral in the strategy, also other 50% of the respondents are Satisfied on the said strategy.

Having weekly orientations to parents to discuss how to execute the lesson and advice possible activities for their child

4 responses

Figure 1.3 shows the result of how effective the strategy of having weekly orientations to parents to discuss how to execute the lesson and advise possible activities for their child at School A. It can be gleaned that 50% of the respondents answered neutral in the strategy, also other 50% of the respondents are Very Satisfied on the said strategy.

Module modification

4 responses

Figure 1.4 shows the result of how effective the strategy of module modification at School A. It can be gleaned that 100% of the respondents are Satisfied in the strategy.

Checking students through house to house visitation
4 responses

In **Figure 1.5**, it shows the result of how effective the strategy of checking the students through house-to-house visitation at School A. It can be gleaned that 50% of the respondents are Satisfied in the strategy, also other 50% of the respondents are Very Satisfied on the said strategy.

The use of big book where students can draw, trace numbers, and write
4 responses

In **Figure 1.6**, it shows the result of how effective the strategy of using big books where in students can draw, trace numbers and write at School A. It can be gleaned that 25% of the respondents answered neutral in the strategy, while 75% of the respondents are Satisfied on the said strategy.

Legends:	
Figure 1.1- Through group chat	Figure 1.4- Module Modification
Figure 1.2- Through Video and phone call	Figure 1.5- House-to-House Visitation
Figure 1.3- Weekly Orientation	Figure 1.6- Big Books

The Figure above summarizes the most effective strategy used by STSA-1 at School A, which is the checking of students through group chat messages (Figure 1.1).

B. School B

The graphs below depict the responses of parents of learners with disability at School B. STSA-2 at School B use the following strategies: providing modules, checking students via video call and phone call, and module modification.

Giving of Modules
4 responses

In **Figure 2.1**, it shows the result of how effective the strategy of the use of modules at School B. It can be gleaned that 100% of the respondents are Very Satisfied on the said strategy.

Checking the students through video call and phone calls
4 responses

In **Figure 2.2**, it shows the result of how effective the strategy of checking the students through video call and phone call at School B. It can be gleaned that 50% of the respondents answered neutral in the strategy, while the other 50% of the respondents are Satisfied on the said strategy.

Module modification
 4 responses

In **Figure 2.3**, it shows the result of how effective the strategy module modification at School B. It can be gleaned that 75% of the respondents are Satisfied in the strategy, while 25% of the respondents are Very Satisfied on the said strategy.

- Legends:
- Figure 2.1- Giving of Modules
 - Figure 2.2- Through Video and phone call
 - Figure 2.3- Module Modification

The Figure above summarizes the most effective strategy used by STSA-2 at School B, which is the giving of modules or modular strategy (**Figure 2.1**).

C. School C

The graphs below depict the responses of parents of learners with disability at School C.

STSA-3 at School C use the following strategies: checking pupils using group chat messages, delivering modules every 15 days, having virtual recognition to reward students' work and success, using talking books, and module modification.

Checking the students through group chat messages
4 responses

In **Figure 3.1**, it shows the result of how effective the strategy of checking the students through group chat messages at School C. It can be gleaned that 75% of the respondents answered neutral in the strategy, while 25% of the respondents are Satisfied on the said strategy.

Giving modules every 15 days
4 responses

In **Figure 3.2**, it shows the result of how effective the strategy of using and giving modules every 15 days at School C. It can be gleaned that 100% of the respondents are Very Satisfied on the said strategy.

Having virtual recognition to recognize the effort and progress of students
4 responses

In **Figure 3.3**, it shows the result of how effective the strategy of having virtual recognition to recognize the effort and progress of students at School C. It can be gleaned that 100% of the respondents are Satisfied on the said strategy.

Module modification
4 responses

In **Figure 3.4**, it shows the result of how effective the strategy of module modification at School C. It can be gleaned that 25% of the respondents are Satisfied in the strategy, and 75% of the respondents are Very Satisfied on the said strategy.

The use of talking books
 4 responses

In **Figure 3.5**, it shows the result of how effective the strategy of using talking books at School C. It can be gleaned that 25% of the respondents answered neutral in the strategy, while 75% of the respondents are Satisfied on the said strategy.

Legends:	
Figure 3.1- Through group chat	Figure 3.4- Module Modification
Figure 3.2- Giving of Modules Every 15 days	Figure 3.5- The use of Talking Books
Figure 3.3- Virtual Recognition	

The Figure above summarizes the most effective strategy used by STSA-3 at School C, which is the giving of modules every 15 days (Figure 3.2).

D. School D

The graphs below depict the responses of parents of learners with disability at School D. STSA-4 at School D employ tactics such as one-hour online classes, the use of songs to capture children's attention, and house-to-house visitation.

Through One hour online class
 4 responses

In **Figure 4.1**, it shows the result of how effective the strategy of one-hour online class at School D. It can be gleaned that 100% of the respondents are Very Satisfied on the said strategy.

Through the use of songs to catch students attention
 4 responses

In **Figure 4.2**, it shows the result of how effective the strategy of the use of songs to catch students' attention at School D. It can be gleaned that 50% of the respondents are Satisfied, while the other 50% are Very Satisfied on the said strategy.

Through House Visitation
 4 responses

In **Figure 4.3**, it shows the result of how effective the strategy of house-to-house visitation at School D. It can be gleaned that 50% of the respondents answered neutral, 25% are Satisfied, and the other 25% are Very Satisfied on the said strategy.

Legends:

Figure 4.1- One Hour Online Class

Figure 4.2- The use of Songs

Figure 4.3- House-to-House Visitation

The Figure above summarizes the most effective strategy used by STSA-4 at School D, which is the one-hour online class (Figure 4.1).

SUMMARY

During the COVID-19 Pandemic, the teaching and learning process shifts to a distance mode. Students can learn online or in a modular format. The researchers picked learners with disability to study because they are among those children who have been most impacted by the abrupt change in educational pedagogy brought about by Covid-19. That is why, the overarching goal of this research is to identify the challenges and strategies for educating learners with disabilities during the COVID-19 pandemic.

This study has three goals: first, to identify the various challenges that teachers face when educating students with disabilities; second, to determine the various strategies used by teachers in the education of students with disabilities; and finally, to determine the most effective strategies used by teachers in the education of students with disabilities.

We used a purposive data collection technique for the respondents to collect specific data when gathering the data. Four (4) SPED coordinators and teachers participated in unstructured interviews conducted via video call or in-person with voice recording. During this time, sixteen (16) parents used a Google form to complete a Likert scale questionnaire. The data gathered by the teachers was transcribed into writings.

After we have gathered the data, we came up with a result. On the first research question ‘What are the various challenges that teachers are facing in educating Learner’s with disability these times of pandemic?’ based from the four (4) coordinators we have interviewed the challenges they are facing are: (1) disobedience of students from their parents; (2) behavior tantrums; (3) selective of whom to teach them; (4) difficulty in developing modules and activities; (5) reliability of responses to students modules; (6) ineffectiveness of the use of Online Platform; (7) attention span; and (8) learning environment

On the second research question about ‘What are the various strategies that teachers employ in educating Learner’s with disability these times of pandemic?’ based from the four (4) coordinators we have interviewed the different strategies they are using are: (1) checking students via group chat messages, (2) checking students via video call and phone call, (3) having weekly orientations for parents to discuss how to execute the lessons and give some advice on possible activities for their child, (4) module modification, (5) checking students via house-to-house visitation, (6) using big books, (7) offering modules, (8) delivering modules every 15 days, (9) using virtual recognition to reward students' work and success, (10) using talking books, (11) one-hour online classes, and (12) using songs to capture children's attention.

And lastly, on the research question about ‘What is the most effective strategies among those employed by teachers in educating learners with disability these times of pandemic?’ based from the result of us google form questionnaire given to parents, the most effective strategy used by teachers at School A is the checking of students through group chat messages. The most effective strategy at School B is the provision of modules, also known as a modular strategy. The most effective strategy at School C is to give modules every 15 days. The one-hour online class is the most effective strategy at School D.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, the following conclusions were reached:

1. Special education teachers face more challenges in educating learners with disabilities, particularly during pandemics, than they do in face-to-face settings, such as;
 - a. disobedience of students from their parents;
 - b. behavior tantrums;
 - c. selective of whom to teach them;
 - d. difficulty in developing modules and activities;
 - e. reliability of responses to students' modules;
 - f. ineffectiveness of the use of Online Platform;
 - g. attention span; and
 - h. learning environment
2. Because those with heart disease and illnesses were given a chance or opportunity to learn during the pandemic, the number of learners with disabilities enrolled increased.
3. Learners with disabilities cannot work on their own; they require the assistance of their teacher and parents, even if they are included in the mainstream, in contrast to normal students who can be self-sufficient in their learning.
4. Learners with disabilities fear their teachers more than their parents; students are more likely than parents to obey their teacher's command.
5. Special Education teachers work hard to modify student modules provided by the Department of Education; they modify it based on the ability of their students, so that it is not a burden for students with disabilities to answer the module.
6. The special education teachers collaborate and conduct extensive research on how to create successful activities and modules for disabled learners.
7. During online education, parents became the teacher of their child at home. Unlike face-to-face education, where learners spent the majority of their time studying with their teacher, parents now

review and ask special education teachers for advice on what to do and how to do and teach the specific module or activity.

8. Different strategies are being implemented and used in educating learners with disabilities during online education at the various schools in Daet, Camarines Norte that offer special education. However, the majority of the four (4) schools that we visited, as well as the coordinators and teachers that we interviewed, use the strategy of:

- Checking students via group chat messages;
- Checking students via video call and phone call;
- Having weekly orientation for parents;
- Module modification;
- Checking students via house-to-house visitation;
- Offering modules;
- Using of big books;
- Delivering modules every 15 days;
- Using virtual recognition to reward students;
- Using of talking books;
- One-hour online class;
- Using songs to capture students' attention.

9. We, also concluded that special education teachers doubled the work during online education, and educating learners with disability requires lot of patience, love and passion.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on our findings, we have made the following recommendations.

1. Teachers may be active in messaging and informing parents of students with disability on group chat. Parents may meet with the teacher on a weekly basis to inform them about their child so that the teacher can advise them on what to do and what is best, and so that the teacher is aware of the progress and situation of their students.
2. The module may be modified and have less activity so that students are not overburdened; the module may also meet the students' abilities. Furthermore, those students who are on the mainstream may have at least one module that is not identical to the modules given to regular students.
3. The module given to disabled students may have a long deadline because they only have a short time to study and sometimes have tantrums and are unable to focus. They may lose interest in studying. It is recommended that they study for two (2) to three (3) hours per day, no more.

4. In online class, it is much better if the teacher creates an area where the students can feel as if they are in an actual classroom. Also, parents may do the same for their child's area, so that students feel and realize that she or he needs to learn and listen to the teacher, rather than play.
5. If possible students may see their teachers, play with them, and ask them how they are doing in terms of learning and life.
6. The activities may be more engaging; it is preferable if the activities are similar to games, so that students feel as if they are playing; in this way, they will enjoy and learn at the same time.
7. Teachers, parents, and co-parents may develop good communication and relationships because, in the event of a pandemic, they must rely on one another for the sake of their children. They may cheer and motivate each other when they are tired, don't know what to do, or are having a problem. In this way, it will lessen the burden that parents feel, especially now that they have become their child's teacher.
8. Learners with disabilities may always be supported and assisted by their parents or guardians, as they are unable to work alone. It is their responsibility as parents and guardians to meet their needs. And also, appreciate and praises students.
9. Finally, no matter how difficult it is, the best way is to put love into everything that has been done. Educating learners with disabilities requires more effort, time, money, attention, energy, and patience than appears to be tiring, but educating them would be easy because of love for these children.

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